

The activities of the internal affairs bodies in the 70s of the 20th century in order to ensure order in the society

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Abstract: In 1970, a number of works were carried out to provide the internal affairs bodies with highly qualified and leaders, and the operation of a number of educational institutions at the level of the union affects the increase of experience and qualified personnel in police bodies. a very difficult situation has come. The article talks about the activities of the internal affairs body in maintaining peace in the society.

Key words: Surkhandarya district, Soviet authorities, internal affairs bodies, criminal investigation department, Workers' militia.

Introduction. The Regulation on the militia, approved in August 1962, played an important role in improving the activities of the militia. According to the regulation, it is stipulated that mature citizens with work ethic and loyalty to the Motherland will be admitted to the police force. In the regulation, it is noted that the police officers should be dignified, brave, vigilant and well-trained, they should selflessly perform their duties without sacrificing their knowledge and strength, if necessary, even their lives.

Materials and Methods.

Based on the decision of the party and the government, in 1963 the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Republic approved the Regulation on the Red Flag of the police. Based on the decisions of the party and the government and the requirements of the new Regulation, great work has been done to provide personnel to the militia[1;100]. The presidium of the former Supreme Soviet of the USSR granted the right to conduct preliminary investigations in public order agencies with the decree of April 6, 1963, in order to strengthen the fight against crime, further strengthen the legislation and expand the democratic basis of criminal justice. Based on this decree, the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Uz.SSR issued a decree on April 27, 1963 "On Amendments to the Code of Criminal Procedure of the Uzbek SSR"[2;95]. In it, the types of crimes that the investigators of the JTS offices carry out preliminary investigations were determined. According to this, an investigative department was created in the Ministry of Internal Affairs of our region, and first,

internal service lieutenant colonel Georgy Aleksandrovich Brook was appointed as its head.

The task of strengthening the fight against crime and strengthening public order in the country requires that it can be solved only when the political educational work is improved in the internal affairs bodies, first of all, in the police. Therefore, on the basis of the decision of the Central Committee of the former party on August 25, 1965, services dealing with political and educational work were established in the police.

On the basis of the above-mentioned decisions, highly educated, conscientious lawyers, Komsomol and party members of various specialties began to work at the Surkhan militia with referrals. For example: Ulash Saimov, Rozi Norkulov, Holli Javliyev, Qambar Mirzayev, Valiql Kattayev, Muhammad Boboyev, Tukhta Mamatkulov, Ramazon Haynazarov, Norqul Nuraliyev, Jura Arniyazov, Abray Musurmongulov, Ibrahim Bobojonov, Chori Karayev, Valijon Dadabov and others are among them[4] .

It should be noted that from the beginning of the 60s, local women began to work as officers in police departments. Khurramova Almos Avazovna (1962), Choriyeva Muqaddam (1966), Arziyeva Ugiloy (1969) are the first. They worked flawlessly for the peace of our nation for many years in the internal affairs agencies [5].

Life experience has shown that the dissolution of the Union and Republic Ministries of Internal Affairs has led to difficulties in maintaining public order, coordinating the work of republican agencies, and in determining the internal structure and staff of some police departments in the normative solution of some issues of the law enforcement service. The inter-republic popularization of the experiences of the fight against crime and the use of the latest achievements of science and technology in this fight [3; 66]. Therefore, in July 1966, the party and the government considered the issue of strengthening the fight against the violation of public order in the country. In the decision taken on this issue, the wishes of workers, public organizations and state bodies to end bullying and other anti-social events were expressed. As a result, in accordance with the Decree of OSP dated July 26, 1966, the Union-Republican Ministry of Public Order Preservation was established in order to provide unified operational leadership of the activities of public order preservation agencies in the fight against crime. By the decree of the OSP of Uzbekistan dated July 29, 1966, the Republican JTSV was transformed into the Union-Republic Ministry of Public Order Maintenance of the Uzbek SSR[6].

By 1966, the Ministry of Public Order of the Republic issued an order to transform the criminal investigation and investigative teams of the large police departments with difficult operational conditions into units in order to strengthen the fight against crime. Accordingly, for the first time in the police stations of Termiz city and Denov district of our region, criminal investigation and criminal investigation units were established [7].

Results and discussion.

Ne'matjon Kuchukov, Yevgeiy Nikolayevich Kuzovchikov, the first heads of the criminal investigation unit worked in the Termiz city police department, and Rahmat Ahmedov, Muhammad Otakulovych Boboyev worked in the BHSS unit[1;204]. In November 1968, by the Decree of the OSP, JTSB was transformed into the Ministry of Internal Affairs, and the main issue was focused on improving the organizational structure of internal affairs agencies and improving its management. As a result of the reconstruction, the Department of Internal Affairs was established in Surkhandarya region [8]. Departments of internal affairs were created on the basis of city and district police departments, and the apparatuses of investigation, state fire control and correctional work were integrated into them.

As a result, now not only the police, but all internal affairs bodies have become departments of executive committees. On November 19, 1968, a decision was made to strengthen the militia. In it, it was demanded to strengthen and expand the connection of the police bodies with the people, public organizations and collectives of workers. Police bodies are tasked with relying on the public's support in preventing crime and fighting crime.

Conclusion.

For this purpose, in 1969, a decision was made to send 20,000 communists and Komsomol members to work in police bodies. It was decided to send workers to the police. With this, a principled new procedure was introduced to send the best representatives of workers' communities to the police bodies, after discussing them at the meetings of the former party, Komsomol and trade unions. In this regard, the party and executive committees of the Surkhandarya region also made relevant decisions, and as a result, on the initiative of the party, Komsomol and trade unions, hundreds of local personnel were sent to serve in internal affairs agencies.

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